

Predictive validity of daily sequential organ failure assessment (SOFA)-2 scores for 30-day mortality

Study protocol v 1.0, 18 November 2025

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Background

The sequential organ failure assessment (SOFA)-1 score has been used to quantify organ dysfunction since its creation in 1994 (1). A recent large-scale recalibration effort, incorporating data from more than three million ICU admissions worldwide, resulted in the development of the updated SOFA-2 scoring system (2). Although SOFA-2 demonstrated discrimination for mortality comparable to SOFA-1 on the first day of ICU admission, substantial recalibration occurred in approximately half of the cases, better reflecting contemporary clinical practice.

Several gaps remain in the evaluation of SOFA-2. First, the score was validated using ICU mortality, an outcome that can be influenced by local discharge policies, bed availability, and the structure of step-down care, potentially limiting comparability across settings. Second, validation efforts focused primarily on day-1 SOFA values; daily SOFA-2 trajectories were only presented for a subgroup of patients, largely drawn from US cohorts. Broader assessment of daily recalibration patterns and predictive performance over time is therefore needed. Third, the relative contributions of the individual SOFA-2 subscores to the risk of 30-day mortality has not been investigated, which limits the interpretation of changes in total SOFA score. Finally, the original SOFA-2 study did not describe comorbidity distributions. This omission is important because acute organ dysfunction and underlying chronic disease may have distinct relationships with mortality risk.

Aims

This study aims to compare daily SOFA-2 and SOFA-1 trajectories during the first week in ICU, assess their reclassification behavior, compare their predictive performance for 30-day mortality over time, overall and in subgroups expected to have different age and comorbidity distributions, and to describe the relative predictive values of the individual subscores over days 1-7.

Hypothesis

We hypothesize that a significant proportion of ICU admissions would be reclassified when using SOFA-2 instead of SOFA-1, and that such reclassification would improve the predictive validity for 30-day mortality.

Study design

Retrospective observational study.

Study population

We will screen all patients admitted to four ICUs at the Karolinska University Hospitals (Solna site and Huddinge site), Stockholm, Sweden, between January 2010 and June 2021.

Inclusion criteria

- Admissions recorded in the ICU patient data monitoring system (PDMS)

Exclusion criteria

- Admissions without a valid social security number
- Patients admitted from ICUs outside the participating hospitals

Data sources

ICU drug treatments, laboratory values, blood gas parameters, monitor data, hourly urine output data, respiratory support data, renal replacement therapy data, and demographic data is collected from the PDMS Centricity Critical Care (GE Healthcare, Chicago, IL). Comorbidity data (International Classification of Diseases, 10th Revision codes), microbiology data, and date of death is collected from the hospital electronic health record system Take Care (CompuGroup Medical, Koblenz, Germany).

Primary outcome

The primary outcome of this study will be 30-day all-cause mortality.

Secondary outcomes

The secondary outcome will be ICU mortality

Definitions of SOFA-1 and SOFA-2

We will use a previously developed and validated algorithm for SOFA-1 score calculations. The algorithm will be adapted to include the updated score definitions and thresholds presented in the SOFA-2 publication. We will calculate total SOFA-1 and SOFA-2 scores for ICU day 1-7 as well as mean and maximum SOFA-1 and SOFA-2 scores for the entire ICU stay. Daily delta SOFA-1 and SOFA-2 scores will be calculated as:

- The change in SOFA score on each day (day 2-7) relative to day 1
- The change in SOFA score on each day (day 2-7) relative the preceding day

In all primary analyses, missing data for day 1 SOFA will be handled using normal-value imputation for each organ-specific domain. Missing data on subsequent

days will be imputed using last-observation-carried-forward. In sensitivity analyses we will use multiple imputation on ICU day 1-7.

Definitions of comorbidities and sepsis

Selected comorbidities will be defined according to a revised Swedish version of the Charlson comorbidity index:

- Renal disease (including moderate or severe kidney disease)
- Liver disease (including mild to severe liver disease)
- Cardiovascular disease (including myocardial infarction, congestive heart failure, peripheral vascular disease, and cerebrovascular disease)
- Pulmonary disease (including chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and other chronic pulmonary disease)
- Malignancy (including any malignancy, leukaemia, lymphoma, and metastatic cancer)

Sepsis at admission will be defined according to the sepsis-3 criteria.

Statistical analysis plan

The primary exposure variables will be SOFA-1 and SOFA-2 on ICU day 1. However, daily SOFA scores will also be assessed in the following analyses. Whenever multiple comparisons are present in an analysis, confidence intervals and p-values will be Bonferroni-adjusted accordingly.

Distribution

Daily SOFA-1 and SOFA-2 distributions and mortality distributions will be presented as proportions (95% CI).

Reclassification

On ICU day 1-7, reclassification between SOFA-1 and SOFA-2 scores will be assessed in the following categories and presented as proportions (95% CI):

1. SOFA-2 = SOFA-1 (reference group)
2. SOFA-2 > SOFA-1
3. SOFA-2 < SOFA-1

We will conduct a logistic regression analysis using category 2 and 3 as exposure variables (with category 1 as reference category) and mortality as outcome variable. An interaction term between ICU-day and category will be included in the regression model.

Predictive validity

We will assess predictive validity for mortality using the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUROC) for daily total SOFA-1, total SOFA-2, delta SOFA-1, delta SOFA-2, and for mean SOFA-1, mean SOFA-2, maximum SOFA-1, and maximum SOFA-2. The DeLong method will be used to estimate 95% CIs and to compare AUROCs.

Subscore contributions

The AUROCs of models incorporating only a single subscore will be computed for days 1-7, and the interaction between ICU day and odds ratio for death per 1-point increase in subscore will be assessed in a multivariate, cluster-robust logistic regression model.

Sensitivity analyses

As sensitivity analyses, we will reassess predictive validity of total SOFA scores after multiple imputation with chained equations of missing data on day 1-7.

Subgroup analyses

We will assess predictive validity for SOFA-1 and SOFA-2 in patients with sepsis at admission and in patients admitted after trauma.

Sample size considerations

We expect a sample size of approximately 30,000 consecutive ICU admissions. No formal power calculation will be performed.

Ethical considerations

This study was approved by the Swedish Ethical Review Authority (approval number 2022-06005-01) with a waiver of informed consent.

References

1. Vincent JL, Moreno R, Takala J, et al. The SOFA (Sepsis-related Organ Failure Assessment) score to describe organ dysfunction/failure: on behalf of the working group on sepsis-related problems of the European Society of Intensive Care Medicine. *Intensive Care Med.* 1996;22(7):707-710. doi:10.1007/BF01709751
2. Ranzani OT, Singer M, Salluh JIF, et al. Development and validation of the Sequential Organ Failure Assessment (SOFA)-2 score. *JAMA.* Published online October 29, 2025. doi:10.1001/jama.2025.20516.